

PID2020-112967GB-C32 - Meeting Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Rail Passenger Service Planning under Competition.

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the strategy for managing, storing, sharing and preserving the research outputs generated within the project PID2020-112967GB-C32 “Meeting Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Rail Passenger Service Planning under Competition”, funded by the Spanish State Research Agency (AEI).

The project aims to develop mathematical models, machine learning methods and artificial intelligence techniques to support tactical and operational decision making in liberalized railway passenger markets. Research activities include demand forecasting, transport mode choice modelling, railway timetable and pricing optimization, reinforcement learning, simulation of competitive railway markets and the development of optimization and machine learning software.

The project will generate research software, simulation environments, machine learning models, numerical experiment results and datasets derived from simulations or publicly available transport data. The DMP establishes how these research outputs will be documented, stored, shared and preserved according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

Funder

MCIN/AEI/
10.13039/501100011033.

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PID2020-112967GB-C32

Researchers

José Ángel Martín Baos (0000-0002-8456-9215), Ricardo García Ródenas (0000-0002-5092-0070), Enrique Adrián Villarrubia Martín (0009-0002-8006-5711), Julio Alberto López Gómez (0000-0001-6291-6637), David Muñoz-Valero (0000-0002-2509-9911), María Luz López García (0000-0002-2452-5472), Juan Moreno García (0000-0003-2430-145X), Luis Rodríguez Benitez (0000-0002-7665-943X)

Organizations

Universidad de Castilla La Mancha

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: PID2020-112967GB-C32 - Meeting Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Rail Passenger Service Planning under Competition.

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the strategy for managing, storing, sharing and preserving the research outputs generated within the project PID2020-112967GB-C32 “Meeting Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Rail Passenger Service Planning under Competition”, funded by the Spanish State Research Agency (AEI).

The project aims to develop mathematical models, machine learning methods and artificial intelligence techniques to support tactical and operational decision making in liberalized railway passenger markets. Research activities include demand forecasting, transport mode choice modelling, railway timetable and pricing optimization, reinforcement learning, simulation of competitive railway markets and the development of optimization and machine learning software.

The project will generate research software, simulation environments, machine learning models, numerical experiment results and datasets derived from simulations or publicly available transport data. The DMP establishes how these research outputs will be documented, stored, shared and preserved according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

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Organizations:

Universidad de Castilla La Mancha

Contact: García-Ródenas Ricardo (Ricardo.Garcia@uclm.es)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033.

Grants: PID2020-112967GB-C32

Project:

3. License

License: MIT

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

ROBIN (Rail mOBility simulation)

ROBIN is a microscopic simulator for modeling railway mobility in competitive markets, developed to study the effects of timetables, pricing, and competition among railway operators.

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Data Management Plan | PID2020-112967GB-C32 - Meeting Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Rail Passenger Service Planning under Competition. LICENSE:MIT
DOI: - 19/06/2026

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

ROBIN is a microscopic railway mobility simulator developed to model passenger flows, traveller behaviour and travel choices in competitive passenger railway markets.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Python source code (.py), Jupyter notebooks (.ipynb), configuration files, CSV data files, documentation files (.md, .rst), environment files (.yml), figures and reports.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Less than 1 GB.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To make informed decisions

ROBIN is generated to support the objectives of the Spanish national project PID2020-112967GB-C32 by providing a simulation environment for analysing railway passenger service planning under competition. It enables what-if analyses of liberalized railway markets, including passenger behaviour, travel choices, pricing policies, timetable design and interactions between railway operators.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ROBIN was developed within PID2020-112967GB-C32 by the University of Castilla-La Mancha research team.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Industry
- Other

ROBIN may be useful for researchers in transport modelling, railway planning, operations research, artificial intelligence and simulation; for railway operators and infrastructure managers; and for public authorities analysing competition, service planning and market liberalization in passenger rail.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

[ROBIN: Rail mOBility simulation](#)

Transportation Research Procedia

RUIdeRA

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://github.com/JoseAngelMartinB/robin>

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2024.02.021>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

No specific controlled vocabulary is required for the software itself. Descriptive keywords from transport modelling, railway simulation, passenger demand modelling, operations research and artificial intelligence will be used.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

<https://github.com/JoseAngelMartinB/robin>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

ROBIN (Rail mOBility simulation)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The software is publicly available through GitHub under MIT License.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Git is used to access the repository. Python and Conda are required to install and run the software environment.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During and after the project, the software will be accessible through the public GitHub repository. Long-term archived releases will be made available through Zenodo.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At least 10 years after the end of the project, preferably permanently through Zenodo DOI-based archival.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Other

MIT License

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

MIT License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Other

Reuse is supported through open-source licensing, public version control, documentation, README files, environment files, tests and examples. The

repository includes configuration files, source code, notebooks, scripts, data folders and documentation.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Third parties may reuse, modify and redistribute the software under the MIT License, subject to the license terms.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

Direct cost

No additional direct cost is expected beyond the research effort already covered by the project and standard institutional resources. GitHub is used for development and Zenodo will be used for archival.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

Covered by Spanish national project PID2020-112967GB-C32 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and standard institutional resources of the University of Castilla-La Mancha.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. José Ángel Martín Baos (0000-0002-8456-9215)

Software management, repository maintenance, metadata and release preparation.

b. David Muñoz-Valero (0000-0002-2509-9911)

Software implementation and maintenance.

c. Enrique Adrián Villarrubia Martín (0009-0002-8006-5711)

Software implementation and maintenance.

d. Ricardo García Ródenas (0000-0002-5092-0070)

Scientific supervision and validation.

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

Version control, authenticated repository access for maintainers, institutional storage, regular backups and public release management.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

The software does not contain personal or sensitive data. Development copies are maintained in authenticated systems and public releases are shared through GitHub and Zenodo.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Stable versions will be preserved through Zenodo with DOI assignment. The GitHub repository will remain available for active development and community reuse.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

A prediction and behavioural analysis of machine learning methods for modelling travel mode choice

This research output consists of the software, experimental workflow, processed datasets, synthetic datasets, figures and tables associated with the paper “A prediction and behavioural analysis of machine learning methods for modelling travel mode choice”. It supports the Spanish national project PID2020-112967GB-C32 by providing a reproducible methodology to compare machine learning and random utility models for travel mode choice modelling. The output combines reused real-world travel mode choice datasets with newly generated synthetic datasets, and evaluates modelling approaches in terms of predictive performance, market share estimation, behavioural indicators, explainability and computational efficiency.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The output includes newly generated software, experimental results and synthetic datasets. It also reuses existing real-world travel mode choice datasets, which are processed and analysed within the experimental workflow.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

Reproducible computational experiments combining research software, processed travel mode choice datasets, synthetic datasets, trained models, figures and tables.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Python source code (.py), Jupyter notebooks (.ipynb), YAML environment file (.yml), CSV data files (.csv), model outputs, figures, LaTeX tables and Markdown documentation.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Less than 1 GB.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To make informed decisions

This output is generated and reused to provide a systematic and reproducible comparison of machine learning classifiers and random utility models for travel mode choice. The methodology evaluates not only predictive accuracy, but also aggregate market share estimation, behavioural indicators such as willingness to pay, explainability, data efficiency and computational cost.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The output was developed by José Ángel Martín-Baos, Julio Alberto López-Gómez, Luis Rodríguez-Benítez, Tim Hillel and Ricardo García-Ródenas. It is associated with the paper published in Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies, 156, 104318 with DOI: 10.1016/j.trc.2023.104318. The real-world datasets are reused from previously available travel mode choice sources, while the synthetic datasets, processed datasets, experiments, figures and tables are generated within the repository.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers

- Industry
- Other

This output is useful for researchers in travel behaviour, transport demand modelling, discrete choice modelling, machine learning, artificial intelligence and transportation planning. It is also useful for practitioners who need to understand the trade-offs between predictive accuracy, behavioural interpretability, market share estimation and computational efficiency when choosing travel mode choice models.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

[A prediction and behavioural analysis of machine learning methods for modelling travel mode choice](#)

Transportation Research Part C Emerging Technologies

ArXiv

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://github.com/joseangelmartinb/prediction-behavioural-analysis-ml-travel-mode-choice>

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2023.104318>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

No specific controlled vocabulary is required for the software itself. Keywords and terminology commonly used in transport demand modelling, travel behaviour analysis, machine learning, artificial intelligence and discrete choice modelling are used.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

<https://github.com/joseangelmartinb/prediction-behavioural-analysis-ml-travel-mode-choice>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

License Code and experiments of the paper "A prediction and behavioural analysis of machine learning methods for modelling travel mode choice"

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The software and dataset is publicly available through GitHub under MIT License.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During and after the project, the software will be accessible through the public GitHub repository.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At least 10 years after the end of the project.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Other

MIT License

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

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MIT License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Other

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repository includes configuration files, source code, notebooks, scripts, data folders and documentation.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Third parties may reuse, modify and redistribute the software under the MIT License, subject to the license terms.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

Direct cost

No additional direct cost is expected. The output is maintained using institutional resources of the University of Castilla-La Mancha and open infrastructures such as GitHub.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

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b. Julio Alberto López Gómez (0000-0001-6291-6637)

Software development and experiments.

c. Tim Hillel (0000-0001-6872-2235)

Scientific contribution.

d. Ricardo García Ródenas (0000-0002-5092-0070)

Scientific supervision and validation.

e. Luis Rodríguez Benitez (0000-0002-7665-943X)

Methodological supervision.

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

Version control, authenticated repository access for maintainers, institutional storage, regular backups and public release management.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

The repository does not contain sensitive information and only publicly distributable datasets are stored.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

GitHub will remain the primary platform for active development and community reuse.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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